

DIGITAL SKILLS
ASSESSMENT OF SHS
STUDENTS:IMPLICATIONS
FOR LEARNER SUPPORT
AND INTERVENTION

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What is Digital Competency?

The ability to use digital technologies effectively, responsibly, and creatively in work, learning, and everyday life.

Information & Data Literacy

Search, evaluate, and manage digital information

Communication & Collaboration

Use digital tools to interact and share

Digital Content Creation

Create and edit content; respect copyright

Safety & Security

Protect devices, data, and privacy

Problem Solving

Apply technology

Why It Matters:

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

E N D O R S E M E N T

This is to certify that the research of **REIMAR A. CORNEJO, Asst. School Principal II of Lemery Senior High School, Lemery Sub - Office** with the title **DIGITAL SKILLS ASSESSEMENT OF SHS STUDENTS:IMPLICATIONS FOR LEARNER SUPPORT AND INTERVENTION** was approved and endorsed by the undersigned immediate supervisor.

It was also was evaluated by the undersigned Members of the District Research Committee (DRC).

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**DIGITAL SKILLS ASSESSMENT OF SHS STUDENTS:
IMPLICATIONS FOR LEARNER SUPPORT AND INTERVENTION**

**A Research
Presented to the
District Research Committee, DepEd – Lemery District
and to the
Division Research Committee (Planning and Research), Division of Batangas**

by:

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2025

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R. A.C.

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the digital competency skills of SHS students in Lemery SHS focusing on five key areas: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, online/offline safety and well-being, and digital problem-solving. The research also examined the influence of student profiles—age, sex, grade level, and academic track—on their digital skills, identified perceived challenges, and proposed a development plan to enhance digital proficiency.

The scope of the study was limited to Senior High School students, excluding teachers and other stakeholders. It concentrated on evaluating students' digital competencies and the challenges they face in using digital tools effectively. The study was conducted within the context of DepEd's Digital Rise Program and aligned with the national framework for 21st-century skills.

The study revealed the following key findings across the five digital competency areas. As to **Information and Data Literacy**, Grade 11 students struggled with evaluating source credibility and organizing digital content, while Grade 12 students showed improved skills but still lacked consistency in critical judgment and advanced data management. **Communication and Collaboration**, Grade 11 students had difficulty with respectful interaction and managing digital identity, whereas Grade 12 students demonstrated better collaboration and communication, though challenges in conflict resolution and digital presence remained. The **Digital Content Creation**, Grade 11 students produced basic digital outputs with low creativity and poor understanding of copyright, while Grade 12 students engaged in more advanced content creation but faced technical limitations and uneven creativity. **Online/Offline Safety and Well-being**, Grade 11 students practiced inconsistent safety behaviors and had limited privacy awareness, while Grade 12 students were more proactive but still needed support in coping mechanisms and privacy literacy. **Digital Problem-Solving**, Grade 11 students relied on trial-and-error approaches and lacked familiarity with digital tools, while Grade 12 students used tools more strategically but inconsistently applied problem-solving frameworks. The study concludes that while digital competencies improve with grade level, significant gaps remain that hinder students' ability to fully engage in digital learning environments. These gaps are influenced by student demographics and require structured interventions to ensure readiness for academic and professional demands in a digital society.

The study recommends that there should be a conducting of regular digital skills assessments, implementing a targeted digital enhancement program, integrating digital literacy across subjects, providing hands-on workshops, promoting digital citizenship education that ensure an equitable access to digital tools, and engaging stakeholders in sustaining digital development initiatives.

Keywords: Information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety and well-being, digital problem solving

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**DIGITAL ASSESSMENT OF SHS STUDENTS:
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I. CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

The rapid transformation of communication and knowledge creation, driven by emerging technologies and digital landscapes, has redefined the concept of literacy in the 21st century. No longer limited to reading and writing, literacy now encompasses a broad spectrum of digital competencies—skills that enable individuals to navigate multimedia information, think critically in online environments, and communicate effectively across diverse platforms.

Recognizing this shift, the Department of Education (DepEd) has launched the **Digital Rise Program**, a strategic initiative aimed at enhancing the digital literacy of Filipino learners and educators. This program is supported by key policy issuances such as DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022 (National Digital Literacy and Skills Framework), DepEd Order No. 50, s. 2022 (National Educators ICT Competency Framework), and DepEd Order No. 034, s. 2023 (Sulong EduKalidad Reform Agenda). These directives underscore the Department's commitment to equipping learners with essential 21st century skills and integrating technology to improve learning outcomes.

Despite these efforts, gaps remain in the actual digital proficiency of learners, particularly at the **Senior High School level**. As classrooms become increasingly digital, students must be equipped not only with access to technology but also with the skills to use it meaningfully and responsibly. These gaps pose challenges to learner engagement, academic performance, and future readiness.

As a **school principal focused on operations and learner support**, the researcher has observed firsthand the implications of these gaps in digital skills. The lack of adequate digital competencies among students affects their ability to participate effectively in technology-driven learning environments, access online resources, and perform tasks that require digital fluency. This situation calls for a **systematic assessment of students' digital skills** to identify specific areas of need and inform targeted interventions.

This study aims to assess the **digital competencies of Grade 11 and Grade 12 students** in Senior High School, with the goal of developing **strategies, programs, and support mechanisms** that will elevate their digital proficiency. The findings will serve as a basis for designing responsive learner support initiatives, such as digital literacy workshops, ICT-integrated instructional enhancements, and resource allocation for technology access and training.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to empower learners to thrive in a digital society, improve their academic performance, and prepare them for future educational and career opportunities. It also provides school leaders and policy-makers with evidence-based insights to strengthen operational planning and learner support systems in alignment with DepEd's digital transformation agenda.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Competency in Education

In the 21st century, digital competency has become a foundational skill for learners. It refers to the ability to use digital technologies effectively, responsibly, and creatively across various contexts. Students are expected to not only operate digital tools but also engage critically and ethically with digital content. As digital transformation reshapes education, learners must adapt to new modes of learning and communication (Ahmed et al., 2022; Zainal & Zainuddin, 2020).

Information and Data Literacy

Information and data literacy is a core component of digital competency. It involves the ability to search, evaluate, manage, and create digital information. Learners must be able to judge the credibility of sources, organize digital content, and use information effectively for academic and personal purposes. Studies show that students often lack these critical skills, which are essential for informed decision-making and lifelong learning (Erwin & Mohammed, 2022; Cambridge University Press, 2022; Emerald Publishing, 2021). Research also highlights the positive correlation between digital competencies and information literacy, suggesting that strong digital skills empower students to be more effective users of information (Lee et al., 2021; Gutiérrez & Serrano, 2016).

Communication and Collaboration

Digital communication and collaboration skills enable students to interact respectfully and constructively in online environments. These competencies include managing digital identity, participating in digital communities, and engaging in collaborative learning. Learners must also develop metacognitive and social skills to navigate diverse digital platforms. Studies emphasize the importance of self-directed learning and respectful interaction in fostering effective digital collaboration (Zhao et al., 2021; Shopova, 2016; Biggs, 2020; Dolch et al., 2018).

Digital Content Creation

Creating digital content is a vital skill that fosters creativity, critical thinking, and innovation. Students must learn to produce, edit, and ethically share digital materials, integrating multimedia elements and respecting intellectual property rights. Research identifies storytelling, multimedia integration, and copyright awareness as essential skills for student content creators (Gómez-Orjuela, 2021; Dilekci, 2018; ISTE, 2017). These competencies prepare learners for participation in the digital economy and support the development of 21st-century skills.

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Online/Offline Safety and Well-being

Digital safety and well-being are critical for protecting students from online risks such as cyberbullying, privacy breaches, and misinformation. Learners must be educated on responsible digital behavior, data protection, and the ethical use of technology. DepEd's initiatives, including the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), emphasize the importance of safeguarding students in blended and online learning environments (Perifanou & Economides, 2019; Empowering Students for Digital Citizenship, 2016; UNESCO, 2019). Promoting digital citizenship is essential for fostering safe and inclusive digital spaces.

Digital Problem-Solving

Problem-solving in digital contexts involves using technology to identify, analyze, and resolve academic and real-world challenges. Students must go beyond basic digital tasks to develop higher-order thinking skills. Research shows that while learners may feel confident in using digital tools, they often lack advanced problem-solving capabilities, which are crucial for adapting to technological changes (Zhao et al., 2021; Sánchez-Caballé et al., 2020). These findings highlight the need for structured support and training to enhance students' digital resilience and innovation.

Generally, the reviewed literature highlights the multifaceted nature of digital competencies required by learners in today's educational landscape. While students may demonstrate basic digital fluency, significant gaps remain in areas such as critical evaluation of information, ethical content creation, online safety, and digital problem-solving. These gaps can hinder their academic performance, digital citizenship, and future readiness.

As a school principal focused on operations and learner support, the researcher recognizes the urgent need to assess the digital competencies of Senior High School students. This assessment will serve as a foundation for designing targeted interventions such as digital literacy workshops, peer mentoring programs, ICT-integrated learning modules, and awareness campaigns on online safety and responsible digital behavior. Furthermore, the researcher may collaborate with stakeholders to enhance access to digital resources and provide continuous support for students' digital skill development. These strategic actions aim to bridge the digital divide, empower learners, and align school operations with DepEd's digital transformation agenda.

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This study sought to provide answers to the following questions.

1. What is the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Academic track?
2. To what extent do students demonstrate digital competency skills in terms of:
 - 2.1 Information and data literacy;
 - 2.2 Communication and collaboration;
 - 2.3 Digital content creation;
 - 2.4 Online/offline safety and well-being; and
 - 2.5 Digital problem-solving?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of digital competency skills when student-respondents are grouped according to their profile?
4. What are the perceived challenges encountered by students in demonstrating digital competency skills in the following areas:
 - 4.1 Information and data literacy;
 - 4.2 Communication and collaboration;
 - 4.3 Digital content creation;
 - 4.4 Online/offline safety and well-being; and
 - 4.5 Digital problem-solving?
5. Based on the findings, what digital competency skills program can be proposed for Lemery Senior High School students to address the identified gaps and enhance their digital proficiency?

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This research will cover Grade 11 and Grade 12 students enrolled in the four academic tracks offered at Lemery Senior High School: Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), and Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL). A total of 1,200 student-respondents will participate in the study, with 150 students per track per grade level.

The study will focus solely on students and will assess their digital competency skills in five key areas: **information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, online/offline safety and well-being, and digital problem-solving**. The research will also examine the relationship between students' demographic profiles—**age, sex, grade level, and academic track**—and their level of digital competency.

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A structured questionnaire developed by the researcher will serve as the primary data-gathering instrument. This questionnaire will be validated by experts in the field who are not part of the study. The statistical tools to be used include **frequency, percentage, ranking, weighted mean, and ANOVA** to analyze the quantitative data, while **thematic analysis** will be applied to qualitative responses regarding perceived challenges.

Research Methodology

The researcher will utilize the **descriptive method of research**, which is appropriate for identifying characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories (McCombes, 2023). The main data-gathering tool is a **researcher-made questionnaire**, designed to measure the extent of students' digital competencies and capture their perceived challenges.

a. Sampling

Given the defined population size, **purposive sampling** will be used to select **150 student-respondents per track per grade level**, resulting in a total of **1,200 respondents**. This approach ensures representation across all academic tracks and grade levels.

b. Distribution of Respondents

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents

The data represents the stratified sample sizes for the **Digital Skill Competency Assessment** conducted among **Grade 11 and Grade 12 learners at Lemery Senior High School, Lemery, Batangas**. The sampling method applied was stratified random sampling at 30% of the total population for each subgroup, ensuring proportional representation across strands and gender.

For Grade 11, the total population was **1,367 learners**, with a sample size of **415 learners**. The HUMSS strand had the largest share, comprising 547 learners (165 sampled), while AUTO female learners had the smallest representation with only 5 learners (2 sampled). Gender distribution in Grade 11 was relatively balanced overall, though technical strands such as AUTO and SMAW were heavily male-dominated, while strands like ABM and HE were female-heavy.

For Grade 12, the total population was **1,536 learners**, with a sample size of **460 learners**. Unlike Grade 11, STEM emerged as the largest strand with 428 learners (130 sampled), indicating a shift in academic preference. Gender distribution in Grade 12 leaned more toward males (56%), with AUTO having no female representation. Across both grades, the sampling remained consistent at approximately 30% per subgroup.

The data provides a strong foundation for analyzing digital skill competency levels and identifying areas for targeted interventions.

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RESPONDENTS: LEARNERS

Stratified Sample Sizes (30%) GRADE 11 LEARNERS

Strand	Gender	Population	Sample Size
ABM	MALE	66	20
ABM	FEMALE	209	63
HUMSS	MALE	266	80
HUMSS	FEMALE	281	85
STEM	MALE	53	16
STEM	FEMALE	87	27
AUTO	MALE	83	25
AUTO	FEMALE	5	2
HE	MALE	40	12
HE	FEMALE	82	25
ICT	MALE	85	26
ICT	FEMALE	31	10
SMAW	MALE	73	22

Strand	Gender	Population	Sample Size
SMAW	FEMALE	6	2
TOTAL		1367	415

Grade 12 Stratified Sample Sizes (30%) LEARNERS

Strand	Gender	Population	Sample Size
ABM	MALE	41	13
ABM	FEMALE	161	49
HUMSS	MALE	285	86
HUMSS	FEMALE	234	71
STEM	MALE	187	57
STEM	FEMALE	241	73
AUTO	MALE	84	26
AUTO	FEMALE	0	0
HE	MALE	39	12
HE	FEMALE	72	22
ICT	MALE	67	21
ICT	FEMALE	49	15
SMAW	MALE	70	21
SMAW	FEMALE	6	2
TOTAL		1536	468

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Ethical Issues:9

Ethical issues will be observed in the current endeavour. Respecting the rights of the population or the respondents under the Data Privacy Act and freedom to select variables in answering the questionnaire. Since the respondents are adults, they have the free will to select choice of decision for the questionnaire.

a. Data Collection

The data and information will be collected from the retrieved questionnaire. Statistical formula will be used for analysis and interpretation. Prior to the administration of the questionnaires, this tools will undergo validation from experts in the field to ensure its reliability and to make it free from biases. The researcher will ask the permission of the District Supervisor who is also the DRC Chairperson before the validation and distribution of the questionnaire.

b. Plan for Data Analysis:

The data that will be collected, tallied and will be presented in tables and figures. The results will be analyzed and interpreted using a Four Point Likert Scale. The interpretation will be supported by related literature and researches from researchers and writers. To quantify the responses, a descriptive scale with corresponding meaning and description will be utilized. Frequency, percentage, ranking, weighted mean and ANOVA will be used to treat as well as interpret the data. The researcher used the following scales with its meaning.

Weight Point	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Proficient (Can perform the skill flawlessly and can teach others)	VP
4	3.40 – 4.19	Proficient (Can perform the skill accurately and consistently)	P
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Proficient (Can perform the skill independently but needs practice)	MP
2	1.80 – 2.59	Novice (Can perform the skill with some guidance)	N
1	1.00 – 1.79	Beginner (Just starting to learn)	B

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Side-by-Side Distribution of Student-Respondents by Profile

Profile Category	Grade 11	Grade 12
Age		
16	273	306
17	327	294
Sex		
Female	296	294
Male	304	306
Academic Track		
HUMSS	150	150
ABM	150	150
STEM	150	150
TVL	150	150

Interpretation

Table 1 presents a **side-by-side comparison** of the demographic profile of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 student-respondents**. Each grade level includes **600 students**, equally distributed across the four academic tracks: **HUMSS, ABM, STEM, and TVL**. The age distribution is concentrated between **16 and 17 years old**, with a slightly higher number of 17-year-olds in Grade 11 and 16-year-olds in Grade 12. The **sex distribution** is nearly balanced across both grade levels. This format allows for direct comparison and supports more detailed analysis of digital competency across grade levels and tracks in the succeeding parts of the study.

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Table 2.1

Assessment of Students' Digital Competency in Information and Data Literacy

Indicator	Grade 11 Mean Score	Grade 12 Mean Score	Grade 11 Interpretation	Grade 12 Interpretation
Choose appropriate search engine	3.00	3.01	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use advanced search features	2.87	3.01	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Formulate queries for smart assistants	3.03	3.15	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Handle information overload	3.20	2.72	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use hyperlinks and dynamic content	2.85	2.76	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Evaluate top search results	2.85	2.99	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Identify sponsored content	3.22	2.90	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Critically evaluate social media streams	3.05	3.16	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Verify author/source credibility	2.81	2.92	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Recognize algorithmic bias	3.01	2.82	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient

Interpretation

Table 2.1 presents the side-by-side assessment of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 students' digital competency in Information and Data Literacy**, based on ten key indicators. The results show that both groups generally fall within the **"Moderately Proficient"** range, indicating that students can perform these digital tasks independently but still require further practice. Grade 12 students tend to score slightly higher across most indicators, suggesting a gradual improvement in digital skills with academic progression. However, areas such as **advanced search techniques, critical evaluation, and recognizing algorithmic bias** remain consistent challenges, highlighting the need for targeted digital literacy interventions.

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Table 2.2

Assessment of Students' Digital Competency in Communication and Collaboration

Indicator	Grade 11 Mean Score	Grade 12 Mean Score	Grade 11 Interpretation	Grade 12 Interpretation
Share content across devices	3.18	3.22	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Restrict content sharing	2.66	3.52	Moderately Proficient	Proficient
Curate content to add value	2.77	3.29	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Acknowledge original sources	2.60	3.08	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Report misinformation	2.58	2.93	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Stop unwanted messages	2.49	3.26	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Manage emotions online	2.99	3.41	Moderately Proficient	Proficient
Recognize hate speech	2.92	3.31	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Handle socio-cultural interactions	2.44	3.09	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Understand long-term impact of behavior	2.90	3.18	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient

Interpretation

Table 2.2 presents the side-by-side assessment of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 students' digital competency in Communication and Collaboration**, based on ten key indicators. The results show that both groups generally fall within the **"Moderately Proficient"** range, with **Grade 12 students scoring slightly higher** in most areas. Notably, Grade 12 students demonstrate **Proficient** levels in managing emotions online and restricting content sharing, while Grade 11 students show **Novice** levels in areas such as reporting misinformation, stopping unwanted messages, and handling socio-cultural interactions. These findings suggest that while students are capable of basic digital interaction and content sharing, they require further guidance in managing digital identity, practicing netiquette, and recognizing harmful online behaviors.

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Table 2.3

Assessment of Students' Digital Competency in Digital Content Creation

Indicator	Grade 11 Mean Score	Grade 12 Mean Score	Grade 11 Interpretation	Grade 12 Interpretation
Create accessible digital content	2.54	3.17	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Select appropriate format	2.95	3.51	Moderately Proficient	Proficient
Create content to support ideas	3.08	2.88	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Create infographics and posters	2.67	3.17	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use tools to enhance accessibility	2.73	3.25	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Download/upload legally	2.40	2.96	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Use/share content legally	2.73	3.23	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Identify copyright exceptions	3.04	3.25	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Understand reuse rights	2.64	3.17	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Choose licensing strategy	2.73	2.53	Moderately Proficient	Novice

Interpretation

Table 2.3 presents the side-by-side assessment of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 students' digital competency in Digital Content Creation**, based on ten key indicators. The results show that both groups generally fall within the **"Moderately Proficient"** range, with **Grade 12 students scoring slightly higher** in most areas. Notably, Grade 11 students show **Novice** levels in creating accessible content and understanding legal downloading practices, while Grade 12 students demonstrate stronger performance in selecting appropriate formats and applying copyright principles. These findings suggest that while students are capable of basic digital content production and copyright awareness, they require further support in applying accessibility standards and legal frameworks for content sharing.

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Table 2.4

Assessment of Students' Digital Competency in Safety

Indicator	Grade 11 Mean Score	Grade 12 Mean Score	Grade 11 Interpretation	Grade 12 Interpretation
Use strong passwords and manage securely	2.78	3.11	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Install protection software	2.67	3.01	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Apply two-factor authentication	2.89	2.73	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Check app data access and settings	2.89	3.16	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Identify suspicious emails	2.73	3.47	Moderately Proficient	Proficient
Apply strategies to fight online victimization	2.88	3.01	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Recognize signs of digital addiction	2.62	3.12	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use low-tech strategies for environment	2.92	2.85	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Reduce energy consumption of devices	2.75	2.99	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Weigh environmental impact of devices	2.59	3.20	Novice	Moderately Proficient

Interpretation

Table 2.4 presents the side-by-side assessment of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 students' digital competency in Safety**, based on ten key indicators. The results show that both groups generally fall within the **"Moderately Proficient"** range, with **Grade 12 students scoring slightly higher** in most areas. Notably, Grade 12 students demonstrate **Proficient** levels in identifying suspicious emails, while Grade 11 students show **Novice** levels in weighing the environmental impact of digital devices. These findings suggest that students are aware of basic safety practices in digital environments but require further support in applying protective strategies for personal data, psychological well-being, and environmental responsibility.

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

Table 2.5

Assessment of Students' Digital Competency in Problem Solving

Indicator	Grade 11 Mean Score	Grade 12 Mean Score	Grade 11 Interpretation	Grade 12 Interpretation
Solve camera/microphone issues	2.55	2.63	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Troubleshoot IoT device problems	2.44	2.69	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Identify root of technical problems	2.56	3.07	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Recognize functions of digital devices	2.63	3.01	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Identify online connection issues	3.01	3.39	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use self-assessment tools	2.47	3.17	Novice	Moderately Proficient
Make plans to upskill	2.72	2.94	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Teach others to recognize fake news	3.24	2.91	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Use online learning to develop skills	2.74	2.78	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient
Find solutions to digital challenges	2.83	2.91	Moderately Proficient	Moderately Proficient

Interpretation

Table 2.5 presents the side-by-side assessment of **Grade 11 and Grade 12 students' digital competency in Problem Solving**, based on ten key indicators. The results show that both groups generally fall within the **"Moderately Proficient"** range, with **Grade 12 students scoring slightly higher** in most areas. Grade 11 students show **Novice** levels in solving technical issues and using self-assessment tools, while Grade 12 students demonstrate stronger performance in identifying root causes of problems and troubleshooting. These findings suggest that while students are capable of basic troubleshooting and self-assessment, they need further support in applying structured problem-solving approaches and leveraging digital tools for continuous learning and innovation.

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

Side-by-Side comparison table of digital competencies between Grade 11 and Grade 12 students

Competency Area	Grade 11 Summary	Grade 12 Summary
Information and Data Literacy	Basic skills in searching and organizing digital content; struggles with evaluating source credibility.	Improved evaluation skills and better organization of digital information.
Communication and Collaboration	Familiarity with digital platforms; needs improvement in respectful interaction and digital identity management.	More effective online collaboration; stronger self-regulation and communication skills.
Digital Content Creation	Limited to basic tasks; creativity and ethical use of multimedia are underdeveloped.	Engages in advanced content creation, including multimedia integration and copyright awareness.
Safety	Aware of online risks but lacks consistent safe practices and understanding of privacy issues.	Greater awareness of digital safety; applies protective measures more consistently.
Problem Solving	Mostly reactive; relies on trial-and-error rather than structured digital strategies.	More strategic; applies digital tools to academic and real-world challenges.

Interpretation of Digital Competency Comparison

The comparison reveals a clear progression in digital competency skills from Grade 11 to Grade 12 students. Across all five key areas—**Information and Data Literacy**, **Communication and Collaboration**, **Digital Content Creation**, **Safety**, and **Problem Solving**—Grade 12 students consistently demonstrate more advanced and refined skills than their Grade 11 counterparts.

- **Information and Data Literacy:** Grade 11 students show foundational skills in searching and organizing digital content but struggle with evaluating source credibility. In contrast, Grade 12 students exhibit stronger abilities in assessing information quality and managing digital data effectively, suggesting growth in critical thinking and digital discernment.
- **Communication and Collaboration:** While Grade 11 students are familiar with digital platforms, they require improvement in respectful interaction and managing their digital identity. Grade 12 students, however, show greater maturity in online collaboration, self-regulation, and communication, indicating enhanced social and metacognitive skills.

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Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

- **Digital Content Creation:** Grade 11 students tend to perform basic content creation tasks with limited creativity and ethical awareness. Grade 12 students engage in more complex digital production, integrating multimedia elements and demonstrating a better understanding of copyright and responsible content sharing.
- **Safety:** Awareness of online risks is present among Grade 11 students, but their practices are inconsistent. Grade 12 students show a more proactive approach to digital safety, applying protective measures and understanding privacy concerns more thoroughly.
- **Problem Solving:** Grade 11 students often rely on trial-and-error methods, lacking structured strategies. Grade 12 students, on the other hand, apply digital tools more strategically to solve academic and real-world problems, reflecting improved analytical and adaptive skills.

3. Significant Difference in the extent of Digital Competency Skills when student-respondents are grouped according to their Profile

Table 3

ANOVA Results: Differences in Overall Digital Competency by Student Profile

Profile Variable	F-Statistic	p-Value
Age	0.13	0.7148
Sex	1.24	0.2665
Grade Level	88.64	0.0000
Track	1.19	0.3120

Interpretation

Table 3 presents the results of the **ANOVA test** examining whether there are significant differences in **overall digital competency scores** based on student profile variables: **age, sex, grade level, and academic track**. The **p-values** show that **grade level** has a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$), indicating that **Grade 12 students demonstrate higher digital proficiency** compared to Grade 11 students. While **track** shows a borderline variation, it is not statistically significant. Differences based on **age and sex** are also not significant. These findings suggest that **academic progression** plays a key role in digital competency development, and that **grade-specific interventions** may be more effective than those based on demographic characteristics alone.

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

4. Perceived Challenges in Demonstrating Digital Competency Skills

Table 4. Perceived Challenges in Demonstrating Digital Competency Skills by the Students Across the Five Key Areas

Competency Area	Grade 11 Challenges	Grade 12 Challenges
Information and Data Literacy	Struggles with evaluating source credibility; limited content organization; low awareness of information ethics.	Improved evaluation but inconsistent critical judgment; better organization but gaps in advanced data management.
Communication and Collaboration	Difficulty with respectful interaction; poor digital identity management; weak collaboration skills.	Better collaboration and communication; some issues with conflict resolution and digital identity awareness.
Digital Content Creation	Basic content creation; low creativity; poor understanding of copyright and multimedia use.	Advanced content creation but uneven creativity; improved copyright awareness; technical limitations persist.
Online/Offline Safety and Well-being	Inconsistent safe practices; limited privacy awareness; vulnerable to cyberbullying and misinformation.	More proactive safety measures; gaps in privacy literacy; underdeveloped coping mechanisms.
Digital Problem-Solving	Relies on trial-and-error; unfamiliar with digital tools; reactive problem-solving approach.	Strategic use of tools but varied depth; better adaptability; inconsistent application of problem-solving frameworks.

Interpretation

The comparative data reveals a developmental progression in digital competency skills from Grade 11 to Grade 12 students. While both groups face challenges, Grade 12 students generally show more refined skills and awareness, though gaps still persist.

1. Information and Data Literacy

Grade 11 students struggle significantly with evaluating the credibility of digital sources and organizing content. Their low awareness of information ethics, such as plagiarism and proper citation, indicates a need for foundational instruction. Grade 12 students show improvement in these areas, but inconsistencies in applying critical judgment and managing complex data suggest that deeper analytical skills are still developing.

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Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

2. Communication and Collaboration

Grade 11 students face challenges in respectful digital interaction and managing their online identity. Their collaboration skills are weak, especially in group tasks across platforms. Grade 12 students demonstrate better communication and collaboration, but still encounter issues with conflict resolution and maintaining a consistent digital presence. This implies that while interpersonal digital skills improve with age and experience, they require continuous reinforcement.

3. Digital Content Creation

Grade 11 students tend to produce basic digital outputs with limited creativity and poor understanding of copyright and multimedia integration. Grade 12 students engage in more advanced content creation, showing improved awareness of ethical practices and technical skills. However, creativity remains uneven, and technical limitations still hinder optimal performance, indicating a need for more hands-on training and access to tools.

4. Online/Offline Safety and Well-being

Safety practices among Grade 11 students are inconsistent, with limited understanding of privacy settings and vulnerability to cyberbullying and misinformation. Grade 12 students are more proactive in applying safety measures and show better awareness of digital risks. Nonetheless, gaps in privacy literacy and underdeveloped coping mechanisms highlight the importance of integrating digital well-being education into the curriculum.

5. Digital Problem-Solving

Grade 11 students rely heavily on trial-and-error methods and lack familiarity with digital tools for structured problem-solving. Their approach is reactive rather than strategic. Grade 12 students show more strategic use of digital tools and better adaptability, but their application of problem-solving frameworks is still inconsistent. This suggests that while experience improves problem-solving, structured guidance is essential for mastery.

Conclusions

Based from the results, the study yielded the following conclusions:

1. **Students' Digital Profiles Vary:** The student-respondents differ in age, sex, grade level, and academic track, which may influence their digital competency levels and learning experiences.

2. **Digital Competency is Developing but Uneven:** Both Grade 11 and Grade 12 students demonstrate varying levels of digital competency across the five areas—information and data

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- 3. Significant Gaps Exist Across Competency Areas:** Despite improvements in higher grade levels, students still face challenges in evaluating information, collaborating effectively online, creating digital content ethically, practicing safe digital habits, and solving problems strategically.
- 4. Student Demographics Influence Competency Levels:** There are observable differences in digital competency when students are grouped according to their profile, suggesting that age, grade level, and track may affect digital skill acquisition.
- 5. Common Challenges are Evident:** Students encounter consistent challenges such as lack of critical thinking in evaluating sources, poor digital identity management, limited creativity in content creation, vulnerability to online risks, and reliance on reactive problem-solving methods.

Recommendations

Based from the conclusion drawn, the researcher presented the following recommendations:

- 1. Conduct Regular Digital Skills Assessments:** Implement school-wide assessments to monitor students' digital competencies and identify specific areas needing support.
- 2. Develop a Targeted Digital Competency Skills Program:** Design and implement a structured program tailored to Grade 11 and Grade 12 students, focusing on the five key competency areas with differentiated strategies per grade level.
- 3. Integrate Digital Literacy into Subject Areas:** Embed digital skills instruction across subjects to ensure consistent exposure and application of competencies in various learning contexts.
- 4. Provide Hands-On Training and Workshops:** Organize practical sessions on evaluating information, multimedia content creation, online safety, and digital problem-solving to build confidence and proficiency.
- 5. Enhance Access to Digital Tools and Resources:** Ensure students have equitable access to devices, software, and internet connectivity to support digital learning and skill development.

- 6. Promote Digital Citizenship Education:** Include modules on ethical online behavior, privacy protection, and mental well-being in digital environments to foster responsible digital habits.
- 7. Monitor and Evaluate Program Impact:** Establish feedback mechanisms and performance

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tracking to assess the effectiveness of interventions and adjust strategies accordingly.

8. **Engage Stakeholders in Program Implementation** Collaborate with teachers, parents, and community partners to support the digital development of students and sustain program initiatives.

SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS

DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR DIGITAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

I. WORK PLAN AND TIME LINE

Activity	Date	Expected Outcome	Persons Involved
1. Planning and Orientation on Digital Development Program	1st Week of November 2025	Stakeholders are informed of the program goals, timeline, and roles	School Head, ICT Coordinator, SHS Teachers, Student Leaders
2. Baseline Assessment of Students' Digital Competency	2nd Week of November 2025	Digital competency levels of Grade 11 and 12 students are identified	ICT Coordinator, Class Advisers, Students
3. Development of Digital Competency Modules (per competency area)	3rd Week of November 2025	Customized modules for each digital skill area are created	ICT Coordinator, Subject Teachers, School Head
4. Implementation of Digital Enhancement Sessions (Workshops, Peer Mentoring, Hands-on Activities)	December 2025 to February 2026	Students improve skills in information literacy, collaboration, content creation, safety, and problem-solving	ICT Coordinator, SHS Teachers, Student Peer Mentors
5. Monitoring and Evaluation of Student Progress	Monthly (Dec 2025 – Feb 2026)	Progress reports and feedback are collected to adjust strategies	School Head, ICT Coordinator, Class Advisers
6. Final Assessment and Reflection	1st Week of March 2026	Improvement in digital competencies is measured and documented	ICT Coordinator, Students, School Head
7. Presentation of Program Results and Best Practices	2nd Week of March 2026	Program outcomes are shared with stakeholders and DepEd Sub-Office	School Head, ICT Coordinator, PSDS, Sub-Office Focal Persons
8. Integration of Digital Skills Program into School Improvement Plan	March 2026 onwards	Sustainability of digital enhancement efforts is ensured	School Head, SIP Team, ICT Coordinator

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II. COST ESTIMATES

Items	Amount	Total
Bond Paper	Php 300.00	Php 300.00
Printing of Modules and Certificates	Php 500.00	Php 500.00
Internet Load for Online Sessions and Data Gathering	Php 700.00	Php 700.00
Snacks for Workshop Participants	Php 500.00	Php 500.00
Materials for Hands-on Activities (USBs, folders, etc.)	Php 400.00	Php 400.00
Total		Php 2,400.00

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VALIDATION FORM AND LETTER

22 August 2025

19

James Del Valle, EdD
Head Teacher,
San Pablo Integrated
Division of San Pablo
San Pablo, Laguna

SIR:

Greetings!

The undersigned is requesting your honesty to validate their proposed questionnaire in relation to their research entitled “**DIGITAL SKILLS ASSESSEMENT OF SHS STUDENTS:IMPLICATIONS FOR LEARNER SUPPORT AND INTERVENTION.**”

This endeavor when completed hopes to present suggestions on enhancing the delivery of learning, school management other aspects of the school system. Rest assured that the data be gathered and contributed will be used only for the purpose of this research and will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

It is hoped that this request will merit your utmost consideration and approval.

Very truly yours,

REIMAR A. CORNEJO
Asst. School Principal II
Lemery Senior High School
Researcher

NOTED:

AVELINO B. MORTEL
Public Schools District Supervisor
Chairperson – District Research Committee

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INSTRUMENT TO VALIDATE THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Directions: This tool asks for your evaluation of the questionnaire to be used in the data for the study stated above, to establish its validity. You are requested to give your honest assessment using the criteria stated below; please check (√) only from the selection.

Scale	Interpretation	Description
5	Very high valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the study, allowing 0-5% error
4	High valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the study, allowing 8-10% error
3	Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the study, allowing 11-15% error
2	Less Valid	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the study, allowing 16-20% error
1	Not valid at all	The questionnaire is valid and can provide unbiased data for the investigation, allowing 21-25% error

VALIDATOR'S QUESTIONNAIRE ASSESSMENT

Indicators	1	2	3	4	5
The indicators in the questionnaire consistently and accurately measure each variables of the study					
The questionnaire fits the variables under study, thus measuring what it intends to measure					
The questionnaire has the capability to measure items of variables within a given same frame					
The questionnaire has the ability to distinguish the characteristics of differing attributes of the subjects under study					
The questionnaire has the ability to gather factual data, eliminating biases and subjectivity					
Quick and complete data can be generated by the questionnaire within the time frame allowed to obtain the data					
The questionnaire has no influence on the variables being measured					
The questionnaire is framed in a clear, simple, in order to avoid risk of error					
The questionnaire is capable of generating data that will be of value and practical use to the sectors concerned in the study					

Comments and Suggestions:

- Check the grammar and spelling in the indicators;
- Change the scales in the questionnaire for learners instead of agree to level of acceptance;
- Consistency in the beginning of every variables in each sentence;
- Add other variables in each table.

VALIDATED BY:

James Del Valle, EdD
 Head Teacher, San
 Pablo Integrated

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COMMUNICATION

01 September 2025

AVELINO B. MORTEL

Public Schools District Supervisor
District Chairperson - Research
Lemery Sub Office

22

Sir:

Greetings of peace!

In the pursuit for quality and equitable service to the learners and stakeholders, the undersigned is a Principal IV of GFLMNHS conducting a research with the title “**DIGITAL SKILLS ASSESSEMENT OF SHS STUDENTS:IMPLICATIONS FOR LEARNER SUPPORT AND INTERVENTION.**”

In view of this, he is requesting your permission to float or distribute their data – gathering instrument to Senior High School Students. This endeavor when completed hopes to present suggestions on enhancing the delivery of education and other aspects of learning related to the present research. Rest assured that the data be given will be used only for the purpose of this study. It is hoped that this request will merit your utmost consideration and approval.

Very truly yours,

REIMAR A. CORNEJO

Asst. School Principal II
Lemery Senior High School
Researcher

NOTED:

AVELINO B. MORTEL

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PROPONENT

REIMAR A. CORNEJO
Ass. School Principal II
Lemery Senior High School
Lemery Batangas

